

LOW COST INSPECTION FOR IMPROVED COMPOSITE WIND TURBINE BLADE RELIABILITY – INFLUENCE OF SENSORS ON COMPOSITE LAMINATE STRENGTH

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ABSTRACT

Wind turbines are an economically-viable alternative and renewable power generation source. Installed capacity is growing by over 20%/year and continued development of wind turbine applications will benefit by ensuring the reliability of wind turbine blade systems. In this work, we extend some previous results on low cost sensors for composite wind turbine blades to determine Loads, Health Monitoring, and Inspection, and Repair. The emphasis of this work is in manufacturing, and the influence of the sensors on mechanical properties. Representative wind turbine blade laminates were made with embedded and post-processing integrated sensors. Sensors studied to date include Polyvinylidene Fluoride (PVDF) piezo electric polymer sensors for strain and transient loadings, accelerometers, embedded metal foil strain gages, ambient humidity sensors, thermocouples, IR transmittance for quality, and fiber optic sensors for a variety of sensing applications. Major conclusions from this work are that low cost sensors are feasible. However, embedding sensors into wind turbine blade laminates will not be trivial; composite/sensor interface and static strength problems were confronted in the present work. Specific results for manufacturing the structural performance of wind turbine blades with sensors are presented, with current, best alternatives for manufacturing.

I. Introduction and Impetus

Wind energy is technically and economically viable for alternative energy generation. Continued development of wind turbine applications will benefit by ensuring the reliability of wind turbine blade systems. In this study, we explore the effects of incorporating sensors into typical composite wind turbine blade laminates and structures. A reliability infrastructure for modern, primary structure is shown in Figure 1 [1].

The approach in Figure 1 is for modern commercial aircraft structures. This approach results in statistically validated, reliable structures, but it is too expensive for wind turbine blades. However, it has necessary elements for a reliability hierarchy of wind turbine blades. Expensive elements include Health Monitoring and Inspection and Repair. Integral, real time sensors in composite blade structures will help the wind turbine industry realize improved reliability. A key question is, *Can an affordable, meaningful approach be developed for wind turbine blade reliability?*

One approach might be to copy the infrastructure which is used for modern aircraft reliability and safety as shown in Figure 2 [1]. Inspections are implicit at all levels and responsibilities in Figure 1, and Figure 2. Hence, a key element to be successful for ensuring the reliability of wind turbine blades is to develop a repertoire of low cost inspection methodologies. This is the focus of the present work. Important parameters which need to be monitored are:

- Static Strength
- Safe Life or Damage Tolerant Design
- Certification Process
- Manufacturing
- Statistical Quality Control
- Defects Quantification
- Health Monitoring
- Operation and Maintenance
- Inspection and Repair

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A variety of low cost sensors for wind turbine blades are developed and presented below to aid in accomplishing the goals and needs for a wind turbine blade reliability infrastructure as presented in Figure 1, and Figure 2.

II. Specifications and Configuration Descriptions

To completely monitor the health of a blade and its environment, numerous conditions must be monitored simultaneously. The structural and environmental information which are relevant to the successful development of a smart wind turbine blade are listed in Table 1 [2]. A preliminary feasibility study has been conducted previously [3], and the emphasis of this work is on the manufacturing and effects of sensors on structural performance. Based on the broad regime of variables to monitor, numerous sensors are needed. A list of the sensors considered is shown in Table 2. A variety of off-the-shelf, low cost sensors was selected for this study, and some specific sensor details may be found in References [4]-[7]. Based on the presumed application, these sensors were all of relatively low profile and minimum mass compared to the blades. The reason for the low profile, low mass sensors was to mitigate drag and inertial forces, which might lead to degraded performance, and to explore the potential embedment of these sensors in the composite architecture of the blades for new construction. All sensors with voltage or current as the basic output were conditioned and monitored with LabView [8], a robust, industry-standard data acquisition and control system. Specialty algorithms within the LabView platform were developed to monitor each sensor. Pre-conditioning circuits for the off-the-shelf, low cost sensors are shown in Figure 3, and Figure 4.

Several of the sensors considered were able to operate without the need for additional extensive signal conditioning, either because the sensor was manufactured with integral circuitry such that the sensor had no need for additional signal conditioning over a given range of inputs, or there was no need for additional conditioning. There were four sensors which did not require any additional signal conditioning or specialty circuits; the 3G Tri-axis Accelerometer from Dimension Engineering (DE-ACCM3D), the ambient humidity sensor from TDK (CHS Series), the Infrared (IR) Emitter/Detector from Fairchild Semiconductors (QED 123), and the fiber optic cables. The Tri-Axis Accelerometer had all the necessary circuitry for proper signal conditioning built into the board housing the sensors. A simple change in voltage would be linearly related to the change in local acceleration experienced in the wind turbine blade. The ambient humidity sensor also had all the necessary circuitry to correctly calibrate and condition the sensor. As with the accelerometer, a linear change in voltage would relate to a proportional change in humidity at a constant temperature and pressure. The ambient humidity sensor is also dependent on temperature to an extent that field implementation may need additional conditioning which is not required for controlled test conditions. Third, the IR Emitter/Detector, did not need any additional signal conditioning, because as a flaw detection device, all that was monitored was change in the current of the detector. A change current would indicate a change in the structural health of the composite. The IR Emitter/Detector monitors laminate quality/damage by IR light transmission. A degradation in transmission (output current) is indicative of laminate degradation (scattering and opacity from matrix cracking). Lastly, fiber optic cables, shown in Figure 4, did not require any additional signal conditioning due to the limited testing with these sensors. Only the signal strength launched into the fiber optic could be monitored using an Optic Wavelength laboratory (OWL) Zoom 2 power meter and a Laser OWL 1550 light source. This was a first step to understanding the reliability of fiber optics as a multi-purpose sensor for wind turbine blades.

The three sensors needing signal conditioning were traditional, well-known sensors; the ubiquitous metal foil strain gage (MFSG), polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) film, and the thermocouple. The metal foil strain gages chosen were a three strain gage rosette, by Omega (KFG-5-120-D17-11L1M2S). This sensor had each gage placed in individual quarter Wheatstone Bridges, as illustrated in Figure 3, to properly monitor the change in resistance of each gage. Recently, these strain gages have been replaced by single axis strain gages manufactured by Omega (KFG-5-120-C1-11L1M2R). The reasons for this change were lower sensor cost and minimal disturbance of the composite material. The PVDF film, due to its signal decay, was conditioned with a charge amplifier configuration [7],[9]. This charge amplifier allowed for monitoring of quasi-steady state loads applied to the structure to which the sensor was mounted. An E type thermocouple was considered because of its wide range of use and ease of implementation. Due to the nature of the sensor a reference junction was needed, however the data acquisition system (DAQ) employed an internal reference junction so no addition hardware was needed [7],[8].

All sensor signals were collected and recorded using one of the two DAQ systems, a National Instruments SCXI 1000 data acquisition system with an SCXI 1303 input/output module, or a National Instruments USB-6229 unit. Both DAQ systems utilized LabView software. The following sensors were incorporated into typical composite wind turbine blade materials and laminates, conditioned, and monitored:

- Embedded into wind turbine blade laminates
 - Fiber optics
 - Foil strain gages
 - Thermistors
 - Thermocouples
 - PVDF piezoelectric sensors
- Bonded onto wind turbine blade surfaces
 - Foil strain gages
 - PVDF sensors
 - Fiber optics
 - Humidity
 - Accelerometers
 - Through transmission IR

Examples of signal outputs from various sensors are shown in Figure 5. In all cases, the amplitude of the signal is adequate for reliable and inexpensive data acquisition and monitoring. Furthermore, the signal to noise ratio is acceptable to obtain quantitative data for health monitoring and in-situ inspections of wind turbine blades.

III. Manufacturing

New Construction

Integration of PVDF, MFSG, and Fiber optics into new blade construction poses a variety of challenges. These include; accurate measurement of desired parameter via the embedded sensor, signal input and output, longevity of sensor, and blade reliability due to flaw inclusion. Each of these in turn can be dealt with through a series of nominally simple, but crucial procedures. Several, techniques to improve material/sensor bonding interface have been explored. Using a 20% by mass solution of Nitric Acid, sensor surfaces have been functionalized by quickly dipping the sensor in the solution and immediately rinsing off any solution still present upon removal from the solution bath with water. The other surface treatment developed was performed by submerging sensors in the Nitric Acid solution for 10 seconds and again immediately rinsing with water. Both techniques were followed with an isopropyl alcohol wash to further remove any contaminants prior to layup. All techniques were compared against un-functionalized sensors that were simply washed with isopropyl alcohol.

Clean signal input and output is needed for successful application of the sensors. The PVDF and MFSG lead wires are coated in PVC. A small portion of the PVC coated wires should be embedded with the sensor to preserve the integrity of the lead wires during laminate extraction; this can be seen in Figure 6. The sensors were held in place with tacky spray glue (consistent with composite wind turbine blade industry manufacturing procedures), and the wires fed through the forthcoming layers, with care given not to perturb the tows in those layers. While laying the peel ply and flow media over the layup prior to sealing the material with a vacuum bag, it is advisable to cut out a 1” square section in both layers. The lead wires should be fed through these sections in the peel ply and flow media. This helps immensely in keeping the lead wires intact during laminate extraction.

Fiber optics are composed of several different segments as illustrated by Figure 7 [12]. The 3 inner layers have been embedded in composite laminates. Embedding fiber optics (FO) into composite laminates is a process that takes a large amount of patience and a great deal of care. By far the largest issue to be concerned with is not exceeding the minimum bend radius in the FO. A PVC coating was stripped from a wire of roughly the same diameter as that of the FO, and placed around the FO as a protective sheath. While embedding the FO into the layup, the sheathing material should be covering the FO everywhere except the gage length of the sensor. A substantial amount of the FO should be outside the laminate in order to have enough to make more than one connection splice if necessary.

Each of the sensors was pulled through the vacuum bag and sealed with tacky tape. For all the sensors the best technique to seal the leaks was to place a second vacuum bag around all of the embedded sensor lead wires and extra FO, as seen in Figure 8. This had the effect of keeping the lead wires mostly free of excess resin during mold injection.

Retrofit

Placing sensors into existing wind turbine blades is not a simple task. Initially, the site of the sensor placement must be functionalized. One effective way of doing this is to wash the location with isopropyl alcohol followed by a 20% by weight solution of nitric acid. The area should be allowed to air dry, or blown dry with compressed air, taking great care to not recover the location with other contaminants. An appropriate adhesive should be used to secure the sensor to the laminate surface. Encasement and enclosure of the sensor should be made with an adhesive that has similar strain and thermal properties as the laminate. Lead wires should be secured to the inner surface of the blades to minimize strain on the sensors.

IV. Testing and Results

Each sensor was incorporated into at least one test laminate. The first few test laminate plates created were used to test the ability to retrieve signal from each sensor. Clearly, from the examples in Figure 5, adequate signal conditioning was achieved. This was true for all of the sensors studied. From these results appropriate adjustments were made to further refine the calibration, accuracy and reliability of the sensors.

As a result of the electrical noise inherent in the primary test location, signal compression was implemented for all sensors tested which were susceptible to such interference. For example, this was completed by increasing the sample rate by a factor of five (5), and averaging the data to the point where the DAQ effectively had a sampling rate of 10Hz. The study to date has concentrated primarily on embedded sensors because these represent the biggest challenges regarding laminates mechanical behavior. Externally adhered sensors which are found to be unreliable can simply be replaced; this is not the case for embedded counterparts. Metal foil strain gages have shown promise for embedment. All tests indicated material strain from those sensors embedded in both matrices but initial tests indicate that those strain gages submerged in nitric acid for ten seconds exhibited the most accurate strain data as compared against the extensometer used.

Embedded PVDF films were also successful in monitoring material strain for all tests. It was determined that a minimal extension rate of 0.08 inches per minute was needed to successfully mitigate the discharge effects of the PVDF materials. It has also been found that the PVDF films coatings are chemically reactive with the vinyl ester resin matrix used which have lead to suspected sensor degradation. Chemical reactions leading to capacitive film degradation can be seen in Figure 9. Despite this, moduli of both surface treatment options developed as well as those films cleaned with alcohol fell within or exceeded the typical testing range of those specimens without sensors embedded as can be seen in Figure 10. This, with the superior sensitivity achieved with the PVDFs dipped in acid, indicated successful bonding between sensors and laminate matrices. Sensor sensitivity values can be seen in Table 3. These results are further confirmed by the FEM images collected from specimens during interlaminar fracture testing; the PVDF delaminates from the matrix. Unsuccessful bonding for sensors only cleaned with alcohol is shown in Figure 11 by the extensive adhesion failure at the fracture surface. On the other hand, successful bonding of epoxy adhesive during interlaminar fracture testing is shown in Figure 12 by the extensive adhesive deposits on the sensor surface at the fracture plane. To date, test parameters have indicated that PVDF films surface treated by dipping the sensor in nitric acid and then cleaning with water and isopropyl alcohol was the preferred treatment. Tensile strength data were collected to supplement this trend with rather interesting results. Coupons with embedded PVDF films treated this way showed significant reductions in strength compared to the other two treatments in both resins, as can be seen in Figure 13. This was in contrast with previous test results and thus; further attention was given to understand these initial results. To eliminate the potential effect of increased thickness associated with the embedment of the sensor, loads at failure were explored. It was found that both resins exhibited similar results to those of the strength tests, as can be shown in Figure 14. It was also found that thickness which most likely increased around the sensor, did not show any significant change on a global scale. While tensile strength evaluation of unidirectional composites is a difficult method of material characterization, it is felt that the initial data are not without merit. It is believed that the cause of this trend is in the possible asymmetric construction of the PVDF used. Dissimilar materials covering the top and bottom of the sensor, most likely reacted with nitric acid and the resin at different rates. This difference could have led to a large asymmetric stress distribution across the sensor which could have instantiated delamination. Further testing is necessary to successfully determine the cause of this trend.

Fiber optics embedded initially showed large fluctuations in signal strength similar to those seen in Figure 15. Signal strength was monitored while the laminate cured to detect potential complications. These initial tests left doubt as to the cause of signal loss and could easily be attributed to handling of the fiber optic during manufacturing and testing as can be seen in Figure 16. Further tests with refined manufacturing and testing procedures to minimize handling of the fibers eliminated a majority of those losses as indicated by the signal test shown in Figure 17. These results indicate limited effects on fiber integrity due to material embedment. Moduli testing of fiber optic specimens

with egress through laminate ply have shown similar result to those found with PVDF films. Moduli of specimen prepared with both surface treatment options show no significant reduction from specimen without sensors except those only cleaned with alcohol. A small reduction in moduli for those sensors only cleaned with alcohol in epoxy is illustrated in Figure 18. This effect is not shared by the vinyl ester counterpart, which is again most likely due to chemical reaction between the acrylate buffer coating and the resin during infusion. FEM images; Figure 19, and Figure 20, further show the effect of these surface treatments on the fiber optic buffer coating bonding. Tensile strength evaluation for embedded acrylate coated fiber optics was performed. A significant reduction in strength of the material was determined for samples with embedded fiber optics, as can be seen in Figure 21. Reduction in Ultimate Load of Samples with embedded Fiber Optics with acrylate buffer coating as compared to sensor less samples.

. Surface treatment using the methods outlined corresponded to an increase in tensile strength of the material. Submersion of the sensor in nitric acid for 10 seconds showed the least reduction in tensile strength Vinylester did not appear to show any difference between treatments. The chemical relationship between the resin and the coatings is most likely the reason coupons with dipped fiber optics were equivalent to those submerged in nitric acid. In a similar fashion to that of the PVDF results, the ultimate loads were used as a metric as seen in **Error! Reference source not found.** The trends of which confirmed the results given by the strength data. Unlike the PVDF films, this trend further confirms that surface treatment is necessary and that the most aggressive method shows the most promise. While the strength results are promising it is felt that further testing is necessary. The cause for this is the lack of reliable data gathered for fiber optics cleaned with isopropyl alcohol. Suspected grip failures in several of the test samples were omitted from **Error! Reference source not found.**

Despite the choice of sensor embedded all specimen show less than 15 percent deviation in moduli from laminates tested without sensors. As indicated by Figure 10, and Figure 18 the vast majority of surface treatment options did not fall outside the testing range for specimen tested with no sensors.

While thermocouples were also embedded they were soon excluded from mechanical testing as an embedded sensor because their limited local perturbation (i.e., stress concentration) of the laminate and the need for successfully bonded embedded strain sensors took priority. However, the coupons with embedded thermocouples failed at a higher load than any of the other embedded sensors indicating minimal effects on laminate strength.

Other sensors were not embedded because potential issues with survivability, perturbation of the composite architecture, or that the sensor would not successfully detect flaws if incorporated in such a manor. A humidity sensor adhered to the exterior of a sample laminate plate performed as designed. Figure 5 is an example of the output signal of several sensors including the humidity sensor in the lower right [2],[3],[10]. The ambient relative humidity in the room during the time of testing was about 25% relative humidity, and after breathing on the sensor it indicated a peak relative humidity of 85%. The installed IR emitter/detector was tested by temporarily introducing an opaque slide between the emitter and the laminate. (Increased opacity is a consequence of damage in a glass fiber reinforced laminate.) This drastically increased the output voltage, as seen in Figure 5 in the lower left, of the detector on the opposite side of the laminate thickness. Lastly, the accelerometer was adhered to the same sample laminate and was subjected to accelerations in all three Cartesian directions; this resulted in the output signal shown in Figure 5 in the upper left.

V. Conclusions and Recommendations

This work extends the feasibility studies in Reference [3] to focus on manufacturing and structural performance of laminates with sensors. All sensors considered were successfully incorporated into composite laminates constructed in a similar manner to that used in the construction of current industry wind turbine blades. MFSG have been successfully incorporated into the architecture of test coupons with no significant degradation of the mechanical stiffness, and were able to accurately report coupon strain. Unfortunately, composite wind turbine blades with glass fiber reinforcements have ultimate strains to failure of several %; well above the utility of typical metal foil strain gages. PVDF films show great potential but have several issues to overcome. First, the dynamic nature of the sensor could lead to errors in accuracy as a static strain sensor. Under dynamic loading, the static and dynamic response will need to be separated. Second, the materials used to coat the sensors chosen are reactive with the chemicals used in vinyl ester resins, limiting their capabilities as an embedded sensor to only epoxy matrix composites to date. Lastly, strength data collected for PVDF films do not show the anticipated trend and is in contradiction to other studies. These studies have shown no significant reduction in flexure strength of the composites. While this study does not share that same fabrics, resins, layup, or sensor location explored in other

studies, this discrepancy warrants further studies. In particular, flexural testing introduces shear between plies and would may produce bonding flaws within the construction. Tensile strength results have also indicated that further testing and analysis of embedded sensors is needed. Fiber optics have proven to be very capable as a sensor for embedment in composite laminates, but the issue of ingress and egress of the fiber optic into the laminate must be addressed in any application to insure survivability of the sensor. All other sensors could be successfully adhered to the interior of a blade or the exterior of the rotor to monitor environmental conditions and loads with limited interference to the blade and overall turbine.

Challenges

Manufacturing

Great care must be taken as to not exceed the minimum bend radius of the FO; during handling, integration, affixing of the ends, or sensor use. Although much more robust, the MFSG and PVDF with copper lead wires and PVC coatings still require careful treatment.

The limiting factor for retrofitting blades with sensors is the need for access to sensor locations. The locations need to have enough working room so the technicians can do a proper job installing the sensors. This may be possible while the blade is still attached to the hub, or the blades may have to be completely removed from the structure and placed in the proper forms for this work to be done safely.

New construction with integrated sensors has shown to be dominated by interface bonding between sensor and material matrix. Current techniques developed to address this issue have shown promise. Constitutive material properties have shown no appreciable change in material stiffness. Additionally sensor sensitivity and accuracy is not largely affected by introduction into this relatively new form of application. This is all very promising and is further reinforced with Field Emission Microscopy images. The bonding of the interface between sensor and composite investigated using a Field Emission Microscope (FEM) machine were very telling. Pictured in Figure 9, a PVDF sensor bonded well over the majority of the film. A small portion of the sensor pictured shows a poorly bonded surface. The poor bonding may be caused by a number of issues. The sensor interface surface may not be fully functionalized, or there may be chemical mismatch. The acrylate coating used on the PVDF sensors and FO has a melting temperature of 90 Deg. C. which is below the post curing temperature of 93 degrees C. The coating may defuse into the resin, and this disassociation of the sensors outer surface from itself may be a source of poor sensor/laminate integrity. Additional images found in Figure 11, and Figure 12, show the contrast between the surface treatment techniques developed. While material stiffness was not significantly affected it is clear that for successful sensor integration these techniques must be performed. For possible continued challenging bonding issues, there is a possibility of using corona-discharge etching to functionalize the surface for sensor attachment [10].

Despite the common idea that fiber optics would be a less disruptive sensor to integrate into composite materials, it is clear from testing that such a sensor must be surface treated to insure proper integration. Once completed, there is no significant change in material stiffness. A Fiber Optic with an acrylate coating is shown in Figure 20 this fiber was submerged in 20% by weight Nitric Acid solution for 10 seconds. As can be seen by the fracture markings at the resin/coating interface, the bonding to the resin was solid with fracture occurring through the buffer layer. The bonding between the Fiber Optic and its acrylate coating is not as robust. This is contrary to Figure 19 which shows the need for these surface treatment techniques.

Sensor Signals

There are several issues, with the signal output from these sensors. The electromagnetic interference introduced by the proximity of the sensor and accompanying wiring to the power generation unit may pose signal and data acquisition problems. Also, the power supplies for the sensors and data acquisition system need to be reliable. Most importantly, analysis of the data collected from the DAQ system is necessary for understanding and interpretation as relevant to Table 1. These data will then need to be utilized for the reliability infrastructures of Figure 1, and Figure 2.

Fiber optic sensors pose several challenges with respect to the signal output. Correct and careful incorporation of the sensor into the laminate during manufacturing needs to be addressed. For example, bending the fiber optic can degrade the signal. Excessive handling can cause signal loss as well, as was seen from Figure 16. If this is correctly avoided, signal loss may still occur as a result of micro bending of the fiber optic across the rather large inhomogeneous materials typical of wind turbine blades. This could result in light loss through the cladding due to

an increase in the incident angle between the light and the core cladding interface. The thermal expansion mismatch between the fiber optic and the matrix of the composite laminate could result in micro-stresses and subsequent signal degradation. After curing, the matrix could potentially put stress on the fiber optic in the radial direction, which could disrupt the core cladding interface or introducing microscopic flaw in the core. Some exotic resins are extremely exothermic during the curing process. This could potentially cause diffusion or degradation of the Fiber Bragg gratings if the temperature of the curing process exceeds the annealing temperature of the fiber optics [12], [13]. Glass is an amorphous solid and solid state diffusion during processing could be some smearing the core and cladding interphase region, further reducing transmission. Strain range mismatch could introduce flaws in the core, cladding, or both. This is due to the difference between ranges of strain to failure in the composite laminate and the fiber optics. Fiber glass can sustain strains up to 1~2% without significant structural failure under tensile loads. With the cladding and buffer layers, the fiber optic systems are larger in diameter than typical glass fibers, and may introduce local flaws. Additional unknown causes of signal loss are still possible. However, the effects are real, and the signal losses in fiber optics due to laminate manufacturing as shown in Figure 16 were common.

Conclusions

The MFSG sensor with a polyimide top and bottom surface; the best surface treatment was to submerge it in a 20% by mass solution of Nitric Acid for 10 seconds, rinse it with water, and wash with isopropyl alcohol, and let air dry. For the the PVDF sensor with acrylate and mylar coatings on the top and bottom of the sensor respectively; the best surface treatment was to submerge it in a 20% by weight solution of Nitric Acid for 10 seconds, rinse with water, wash with isopropyl alcohol, and let it air dry. The best surface treatment for embedding Fiber Optic sensors with acrylate coating was to submerge it in a 20% by weight solution of Nitric Acid for 10 seconds, rinse with water, wash with isopropyl alcohol, and let it air dry.

Future Work

Testing samples with embedded sensors under various load profiles will be necessary for longevity of both sensors and laminate to be understood. Specifically, additional tensile strength testing and flexure strength testing will need to be performed to understand this unexpected and interesting trend found in the PVDF film coupons. Cyclic loading of samples with sensors embedded should be tested to failure. Sensors should be bonded onto existing component size structures and field-tested in order to validate the reliability of attachment techniques and associated data acquisition and control. Increased sample testing will further reinforce the preliminary, but very encouraging initial results. New approaches to quantifying survivability and reliability of the sensors will need to be considered, developed, and performed to fully understand the issues associated with the embedment of sensors into the composite architecture of wind turbine blades as well as external adhesion. The ability of the acrylate buffer layer on the fiber optic to transfer strain into the glass of the Fiber Optic needs further investigation. This may require a collaborative effort with fiber optic manufacturers.

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Table 1. Health and Environmental Conditions to monitor for a Wind Turbine Blade [1]

What to sense	Why to Sense	Comments	How	Where (location)	Rank
Wind Velocity	Extreme wind velocities for monitoring limitations	May already be velocity sensors on turbines, but used to identify possible failure situations.	Wind speed sensor, Anemometer	Top of tower or Nacelle	9
Temperature	Extreme variations to correspond with other data and corrections.	May already be temperature sensors on turbines, but used to identify possible failure situations.	Thermocouple, RTD, digital thermometers	Top of tower or Nacelle	6
Blade Strain	Check for extreme strain along blade length and leading/trailing edges.	Checking for delamination and strain at different positions along the blade	Strain gauge rosette	At various locations along blade: base, middle, tip, leading and trailing edges	1
Moisture/ Humidity	Moisture could affect material properties.	Moisture accumulation along blade.	Impedance moisture sensors	Atmosphere location, Top of tower or Nacelle	5
Angular Position	To correct with other acquired data for efficiency purposes.	Used in conjunction with optimizing efficiency.	In conjunction with other trim adjustment systems.	Base of blades	8
Torque	Possible torsion at base of blades.	Torque could lead to blade failure.	Infrared (IR), FM transmitter	Base of the blade towards Nacelle	10
Loading	Excessive loads will lead to fatigue.	Modeling of design or life purposes.	Associated with Strain	Various locations along blade length	7
Blade Acceleration	Extreme changes in velocity could lead to failure.	To model force excessive changes.	Piezoelectric Accelerometers, Capacitive Accelerometers, MEMS	Internally at tip where acceleration is greatest	4
Blade Tip Deflection	To avoid tower strikes	Keep overall blade tip deflection in check.	Fiber Optic, Infrared (IR)	Attached to base at blade length to sense blade tip position	2

Blade Imperfections	To check for impurities within blade material.	non-destructive ultrasonic testing, cracks, voids	Ultrasonic, vibratory	Ideally along entire blade length	3
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Table 2. Sensors Considered for Implementation in to Blades Condition Monitoring

Sensors	Impetus	Comments
Metal Foil Strain Gages	Reliable, well understood strain sensor with a relatively low profile. Relatively in expensive	Not well known as a reliable long term sensor in an environment where cyclical loading is present. Strain range is considerable less than that of fiberglass composites
Piezoelectric Films	Great dynamic strain sensor, also capable of monitoring temperature fluctuations, without a supply source	Not a reliable static load strain sensor. Also very susceptible to electromagnetic interference
Fiber Optic Cables	Innovative, strain sensor capable of monitoring strain in multiple locations using one fiber. Capable of also monitoring temperature changes as well.	While not susceptible to electromagnetic interference, the sensor integration into manufacturing is formidable due to the brittle nature of the fibers.
Thermocouple	Simple, accurate sensor to monitor blade temperature	Due to the Seebeck effect a reference junction is needed
Ambient Humidity Sensor	Determine humidity levels which might be detrimental to blade longevity	Profile would make embedment problematic as well as potentially increasing drag if placed on the exterior of the blade
Tri-axis Accelerometer	reliable way of monitoring the forces applied to the surface of the blades	size of sensor could inhibit embedment
Infrared emitter	Internal flaw detection	Increased drag on blade, as well as limited viewing window.

Table 3. PVDF dipped in Nitric Acid exhibited superior sensitivity to strain but sensors submerged or cleaned are suitable to the task.

Treatment	Vinylester	Epoxy
	V/ % strain	V/ % strain
Cleaned in Isopropyl Alcohol	2.07	3.66
Dipped in 20% by mass HNO ₃ & cleaned in Isopropyl Alcohol	2.69	5.17
Submerged for 10 sec. in 20% by mass HNO ₃ & cleaned in Isopropyl Alcohol	2.60	4.99

Figure 1. Probabilistic Life Cycle Management [1]

Figure 2. Potential Wind Turbine Blade Reliability Infrastructures (ala modern commercial aircraft structural reliability and safety [1]).

Figure 3. Signal conditioning of all sensors considered to date for this study. [3]

Figure 4. Signal Conditioning and response for the fiber optic cables considered.

3 Axis Accelerometer

Foil and Piezo Strain Gages

IR Emitter and Photo Transistor

Humidity Sensor

Figure 5, Example Signal Responses from typical wind turbine blade composite laminate. [2]

Figure 6, PVC wires inside of laminate with egress to the surface

Figure 7. General Fiber Optic Construction (buffer coating, cladding and core embedded) [12]

Figure 8. Secondary bag to enable reliable sealing around egress of fiber optics from laminate.

Figure 9. Field Emission Microscopy image of poor bonding of PVDF film sensors coating to composite matrix.

Figure 10. Both surface treatments either fell within or very near the typical experimental range of modulus data for no sensor specimens (values normalized to $V_f=40\%$).

Figure 11. Poor bonding of epoxy to PVDF sensor cleaned with isopropyl alcohol prior to embedment. (majority of fracture surface at PVDF sensor plane)

Figure 12. Good adhesive failure of epoxy bonded to PVDF submerged in Nitric Acid of ten second. (minimal exposed PVDF sensor surface at interface)

Figure 13. Reduction in Tensile Strength owe to embedment of PVDF films (normalized to $V_f = 40\%$).

Figure 14. Percent Reduction of Ultimate Load of samples with embedded PVDF films as compared to samples without sensors.

Figure 15. Fiber Optic Signal Strength and Laminate Temperature over curing period. (Signal losses due to microbending and handling)

Figure 16. Visual Fault Locator used to determine locations of signal loss. (Light “flaws: at signal loss regions are a consequence of exceeding the minimal bend radius, microbending, and handling.)

Figure 17. Resolved handling issues show minimal effect on fiber due to laminate injection and curing.

Figure 18. Sample Moduli showed that both surface treatment options fall within typical experimental limits of no sensors specimen or exceeded this range (normalized to $V_f = 40\%$).

Figure 19. Fiber optic with acrylate buffer layer cleaned in isopropyl alcohol prior to embedment.

Figure 20. Fiber Optic embedded in Fiberglass Layup (good composite bonding, poor bonding between buffer layer and fiber as manufactured by fiber optic supplier).

Figure 21. Reduction in Ultimate Load of Samples with embedded Fiber Optics with acrylate buffer coating as compared to sensor less samples.

Figure 22, Percent Reduction in Tensile Strength owe to embedded Fiber optics with acrylate buffer coating (normalized to $V_f = 40\%$)